

Mannich Bases of Salicylic Acid Hydrazide

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Manuscript received 22 February 1978, revised 4 July 1978, accepted 6 September 1978.

A group of Mannich bases of salicylic acid hydrazide have been prepared utilizing different aliphatic, heterocyclic and aromatic amines. These Mannich bases have been tested for antifungal activity against *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Fusarium chlamydosporum*. The percentage of colony inhibition are measured, and the results of the tests are tabulated.

SALICYLIC acid hydrazide is known to possess antituberculous¹, antipyretic², fungistatic³, and diuretic⁴ activities. It was therefore thought of interest to prepare some Mannich bases of salicylic acid hydrazide and to study their antimicrobial activities. A survey of literature shows that the insertion of an aminomethyl moiety in a large variety of compounds has been found to augment the therapeutic value. With this objective in view a few Mannich bases of salicylic acid hydrazide were prepared by taking different amines like dimethylamine, diethanolamine, piperidine, morpholine, piperazine, dipropylamine, di-isopropylamine, dibutylamine, dibenzylamine, dicyclohexylamine, aniline, N-methylaniline, O-anisidine and sulphanilamide.

The reaction was carried out by employing equimolar quantities of salicylic acid hydrazide, dissolved in dioxan, formaldehyde solution (ca. 38%), an amine and few drops of hydrochloric acid under stirring. In some cases it was found that the products get separated simply on cooling the solution, while refluxing of one to two hours are required in most of the cases. Further an acidic medium facilitates the formation of the bases, while a basic medium enhances their separation. The Mannich bases of salicylic acid hydrazide prepared are shown in the Table 1.

TABLE-1 MANNICH BASES OF SALICYLIC ACID HYDRAZIDE

S. No.	Name of compound	Molecular formula	Mol. Wt*		m. p.* °C	%	% Nitrogen		Percentage colony inhibition	
			Found	Reqd.			Yield	Found	Reqd.	<i>F. oxysporum</i>
I.	3-(Dimethylamino-methyl)SH	C ₁₀ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂	206.82	209.24	202-5	53	20.81	20.08	-12	20
II.	3-(Diethanolamino-methyl)SH	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄	270.06	269.29	125	85	15.96	15.60	0	18.5
III.	3-(Piperidinomethyl)SH	C ₁₃ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂	245.90	249.30	111-13	71	16.14	16.85	4	16.5
IV.	3-(Morpholinomethyl)SH	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃	248.68	251.27	174(Dec.)	40	16.47	16.72	0	26
V.	N : N' Bis-3-(Salicylic acid-hydrazidomethyl) piperazine	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₄	435.97	438.47	190(Dec.)	42	19.11	19.16	50	56
VI.	3-(Dipropylamino-methyl)SH	C ₁₄ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂	262.68	265.34	92-95	10	15.93	15.83	-12	26
VII.	3-(Di-isopropylamino-methyl)SH	C ₁₄ H ₂₉ N ₃ O ₂	263.74	265.34	291(Dec.)	60	15.01	15.83	50	31.5
VIII.	3-(Dibutylaminomethyl)SH.HCl.	C ₁₆ H ₂₈ N ₃ O ₂ .Cl	330.10	329.86	220	33	12.23	12.73	-20	26
IX.	3-(Dibenzylaminomethyl)SH	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂	359.55	361.42	220-22	68	11.76	11.62	-20	18.5
X.	3-(Dicyclohexylamino-methyl)SH	C ₂₀ H ₃₁ N ₃ O ₂	346.24	345.46	270(Dec.)	80	12.56	12.16	-14	26
XI.	3-(Anilinomethyl)SH	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂	255.34	257.28	209-11	65	15.62	16.33	10	7.5
XII.	3-(N-methylanilinomethyl)SH	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	269.14	271.30	200(Dec.)	75	14.99	15.48	-10	31.5
XIII.	3-(O-Anisidinomethyl)SH	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃	286.24	287.30	195(Dec.)	60	14.31	14.62	50	44.5
XIV.	3-(Sulphanilamidomethyl)SH	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ .S	332.35	336.35	204-6	86	16.69	16.56	4	-2

SH denotes salicylic acid hydrazide

*Molecular weight determined by non-aqueous titration

*All the m. p.s are uncorrected.

*For correspondence

Non-Aqueous Titration of Mannich Bases of Salicylic acid hydrazide :

These Mannich bases behave as Lewis bases and have been estimated satisfactorily by titrating them with standard acetous perchloric acid^{5,6}.

In case of N : N'-Bis 3-(salicylic acid hydrazido-methyl) piperazine, the molecular weight is four times that of the equivalent weight. 3-(Sulphanilamidomethyl) salicylic acid hydrazide has three such nitrogen atoms, which are ready to donate their lone pair of electrons, so the molecular weight is three times of the equivalent weight.

Structure of Mannich Bases of Salicylic Acid Hydrazide :

Unlike the Mannich bases of salicylamide where it has been established as the carboxamide derivatives⁷, the inductive effect of the phenolic group in salicylic acid hydrazide has been found to be more pronounced resulting in the entrance of the carbonium-immonium cation⁸ at the ortho position of the phenolic group^{9,10,11}, as the usual electrophilic substitution in the benzene ring.

In the present investigation the ir absorption spectra of Mannich bases of salicylic acid hydrazide were taken along with that of salicylic acid hydrazide. The spectrum of salicylic acid hydrazide shows splitted bands in the region 1680-1630 cm^{-1} and 1310-1200 cm^{-1} . These splitted bands are also found in the spectra of Mannich bases of salicylic acid hydrazide¹² suggesting no any change in -CONHNH₂ group.

Experimental*3-(Dimethylamino methyl) salicylic acid hydrazide.*

To a solution of salicylic acid hydrazide (3.04 g., ca. 0.02 M) in dioxan (25 ml.) was added dimethylamine (0.9 g., ca. 0.02 M). The mixture was well cooled and then treated with 38% formaldehyde solution (1.6 ml., ca. 0.02 M) under stirring. 2-3 drops of hydrochloric acid were added and the mixture was left overnight at 5°. It was kept at room temperature for sometime and the separated crystals were filtered and recrystallised from formamide.

By this procedure compounds, IV, V, IX and X were prepared using appropriate amines.

3-(Diethanolamino methyl) salicylic acid hydrazide.

Salicylic acid hydrazide (3.04 g., 0.02M) dissolved in dioxan (25 ml.), was added under cooling and

stirring diethanolamine (2.01 g., ca. 0.02M). The mixture was then treated with a 38% formaldehyde solution (1.6 ml., ca. 0.02M) followed by 2-3 drops of hydrochloric acid. The mixture was left overnight at 5°. 2-3 Drops of ammonia were added to neutralize the traces of HCl and the oil obtained was dissolved in a mixture of petroleum ether and benzene. Few drops of acetone were added and the separated crystals were filtered and recrystallised from chloroform.

3-(Piperidinomethyl) salicylic acid hydrazide.

To salicylic acid hydrazide (3.04 g., ca. 0.02M) dissolved in dioxan (25 ml.), were added under stirring piperidine (1.7 g., ca. 0.02M), and a 38% formaldehyde solution (1.6 ml., ca. 0.02M), followed by the addition of 2-3 drops of hydrochloric acid. On cooling overnight and adding 2-3 drops of ammonia and cooling again, the crystals which appeared were filtered and dried. The product was recrystallised from glacial acetic acid,

3-(Dipropylamino methyl) Salicylic acid hydrazide:

Salicylic acid hydrazide (3.04 g., ca. 0.02M) dissolved in dioxan (25 ml) was treated under continuous stirring with dipropylamine (2.02 g., ca. 0.02M), 38% formaldehyde solution (1.6 ml., ca. 0.02M) and 2-3 drops of hydrochloric acid. The reaction mixture was refluxed on water bath for half an hour and kept at 5° overnight. The mixture was made alkaline with 2-3 drops of ammonia and acetone was added. Separated crystals were filtered, dried and recrystallised from DMF.

Compounds XI, XII, XIII and XIV were also prepared by this method using appropriate amines.

3-(Di-isopropylamino methyl) salicylic acid hydrazide.

Salicylic acid hydrazide (3.04 g., ca. 0.02M) dissolved in dioxan (25 ml.) was treated under continuous stirring with a mixture of di-iso-propylamine (2.02 g., ca. 0.02M) and 38% formaldehyde solution (1.6 ml., ca. 0.02M). 2-3 drops of hydrochloric acid was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for two hours on a water bath. The solid mass separated was recrystallised from glacial acetic acid.

3-(Dibutylamino methyl) salicylic acid hydrazide hydrochloride.

To a solution of salicylic acid hydrazide (3.04 g., ca. 0.02M) in dioxan (25 ml.) was added dibutylamine (2.58 g., ca. 0.02M). 38% formaldehyde solution (1.6 ml., ca. 0.02M) and 2-3 drops of hydrochloric acid. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath for about two hours. The reaction mixture was made alkaline with 2-3 drops of ammonia and acetone was added. The oil obtained was dissolved in glacial acetic acid and hydrochloric

acid gas was passed in it. The separated solid was filtered, washed with some alcohol and dried.

Screening for Antifungal activity :

All the above mentioned Mannich bases were screened *in vitro* against *F. oxysporum* and *F. chlamydosporum* by using Czapek-Dox medium at a concentration of 0.25 µg/ml. The petridishes were kept in culture room at 25±1° and results were recorded after 5 days.

From the experimental data it was observed that *F. chlamydosporum* proved to be more sensitive than *F. oxysporum*. All the Mannich bases were found to possess inhibitory effect of different levels against *F. chlamydosporum* except No. 14 in which slight enhancement was observed. But when tested against *F. oxysporum* only compound No. 3,5,7,11, 13 and 14 were found to possess inhibitory effect and others enhanced the growth except compound No. 2 and 4 where no effect was observed. In such cases where enhancement in growth was observed, it may be noted that these Mannich bases may act as a source of nitrogen. It is not surprising. It is an historical fact that even the first sulphadrag; Prontosil rubrum, showed no antimicrobial activity *in vitro*.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Prof. O. P. Malhotra, Head of Chemistry Department, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi for micro analyses of nitrogen and ir spectra of the samples. The authors are also

grateful to Dr. R. S. Dwivedi and Mr. S. P. Pathak, Department of Botany, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi for providing facilities to carry out fungicidal tests in his laboratory. The financial assistance (U.G.C.) granted by the authorities of Banaras Hindu University to one of us (BNY) is also gratefully acknowledged.

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